

The Law Behind the Paywall

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Abstract - In the European Union, harmonised standards are privately developed technical specifications that define how to comply with public laws, including those governing AI, robotics, and machinery. While this system supports timely and technically informed legislation, it also places legal compliance behind paywalls, undermining transparency and public access. In this article, we argue that such restricted access violates the rule of law. Drawing on the European Court of Justice’s landmark *Malamud* ruling, which held that harmonized standards incorporated into EU law must be freely accessible, we examine the legal and practical implications of this precedent in the context of robotics. Beyond our legal analysis, we provide concrete guidance on how persons in the EU can access harmonised standards in practice and address some open questions—such as whether related technical reports must be freely available and whether read-only access satisfies the rule of law—that remain despite the *Malamud* judgment.

Keywords: Harmonised standards; *Malamud* case; Robotics and Law; ISO 13482; Personal care robots

1. Introduction

From factory floors to care homes, robots and intelligent machines are increasingly governed not by laws but by standards. These technical specifications—covering everything from sensor calibration to safety thresholds—are drafted not by legislators but by private industry. In the European Union (EU), this delegation of rule-making is formalized through a regulatory model developed in the 1980s known as the ‘new

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approach' framework.¹ This framework provided that the technical specifications required of products to be made available in the EU market be specified in part in EU laws that contain essential health and safety requirements, and for the rest in elaborate technical standards.² This model was further refined in 2008 with the New Legislative Framework (NLF),³ which strengthened and clarified the rules on product regulation. The NLF introduced a more consistent approach to conformity assessment, market surveillance, and accreditation of assessment bodies; while preserving the principle that legislation defines essential requirements and standards provide the technical specifications. This approach has allowed private standardization bodies to create the fine print of compliance for EU laws governing many products, including robots, medical devices, and artificial intelligence (AI) systems.⁴

While efficient, this hybrid model raises a troubling paradox: the very instruments that determine legal compliance are often locked behind paywalls. A single

¹ Council Resolution of 7 May 1985 on a new approach to technical harmonization and standards 1985 (OJ C 136) 1.

² Carlo Colombo and Mariolina Eliantonio, 'Harmonized Technical Standards as Part of EU Law: Juridification with a Number of Unresolved Legitimacy Concerns?: Case C-613/14 James Elliot Construction Limited v. Irish Asphalt Limited, EU:C:2016:821' (2017) 24 *Maastricht Journal of European and Comparative Law* 323.

³ European Commission, 'New Legislative Framework' <https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/goods/new-legislative-framework_en> accessed 29 July 2025.

⁴ Kostina Prifti and Eduard Fosch-Villaronga, 'Towards Experimental Standardization for AI Governance in the EU' (2024) 52 *Computer Law & Security Review* 105959.

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robotics standard—such as ISO 13482:2014,⁵ which governs personal care robots—can cost nearly 200 Swiss francs. This means that understanding and complying with the law requires a credit card, not just legal diligence. The problem is especially acute in robotics, where explicit legal categories are scarce.⁶ Unlike ‘machines’ or ‘medical devices,’ the term ‘robot’ barely appears in EU legislation. Which laws apply to robots depend on their features and use case, meaning that robots do not fall squarely within a single piece of targeted legislation. Instead, robots may be regulated under product safety, cybersecurity, or data protection laws, and potentially the recently enacted AI Act. As a result, legal compliance is often achieved through harmonised standards—technical standards developed by European Standardisation Organisations at the request of the European Commission (the Commission) to support the application of EU law⁷—that effectively define what makes a robot safe, lawful, or market-ready.⁸

⁵ ISO, ‘ISO 13482:2014 - Robots and Robotic Devices — Safety Requirements for Personal Care Robots’ 13482 <<https://www.iso.org/standard/53820.html>> accessed 1 July 2025.

⁶ Eduard Fosch-Villaronga, *Robots, Healthcare, and the Law: Regulating Automation in Personal Care* (Routledge 2019) <<https://www.routledge.com/Robots-Healthcare-and-the-Law-Regulating-Automation-in-Personal-Care/Fosch-Villaronga/p/book/9781032239804>> accessed 21 July 2025.

⁷ Regulation (EU) No 1025/2012 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 25 October 2012 on European standardisation, amending Council Directives 89/686/EEC and 93/15/EEC and Directives 94/9/EC, 94/25/EC, 95/16/EC, 97/23/EC, 98/34/EC, 2004/22/EC, 2007/23/EC, 2009/23/EC and 2009/105/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council and repealing Council Decision 87/95/EEC and Decision No 1673/2006/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council 2012 (OJ L 316) 12, art 2(1)(c).

⁸ Eduard Fosch-Villaronga and others, ‘Science for Robot Policy: Advancing Robotics Policy through the EU Science for Policy Approach’ (2025) 218 *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 124202.

For instance, manufacturers rely on ISO 13482:2014 to demonstrate conformity with the EU Machinery Directive for service robots—currently, the only harmonized standard dedicated to non-industrial, non-medical robots that assist people in daily life. Though now under revision, this standard has become the *de facto* legal framework for an entire class of service robot technologies. Regulators, researchers, and users depend on it to assess risks, assign responsibility, and advocate for safety.⁹

Yet, these standards—while not technically laws—function as legal gatekeepers. They provide a presumption of conformity with binding EU laws,¹⁰ and, in practice, they shape markets, determine liability, and steer innovation. When such tools are not freely available, the result is a restricted system where key legal obligations are obscured from public view, undermining transparency, legal certainty, and access to justice—all foundational elements of the rule of law. However, alleviating these problems significantly, the European Court of Justice (ECJ) has weighed in on this issue. In the landmark *Public.Resource.Org Inc. v European Commission* case¹¹ (known as the *Malamud* case), the Court ruled that harmonized standards, when referenced in EU law and effectively made mandatory, must be publicly accessible. The precedent is clear: no one should have to pay to know what the law expects of them.

⁹ Eduard Fosch-Villaronga and others, ‘How Can ISO 13482:2014 Account for the Ethical and Social Considerations of Robotic Exoskeletons?’ (2023) 75 *Technology in Society* 102387.

¹⁰ European Commission, ‘Harmonised Standards’ <https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/single-market/european-standards/harmonised-standards_en> accessed 29 July 2025.

¹¹ *PublicResourceOrg Inc v European Commission* [2024] European Court of Justice Case C-588/21, ECLI:EU:C:2024:201.

In this article, we argue that the continued commercialization of harmonized standards is incompatible with the rule of law. While others have rightly critiqued these standards for privatizing legislation or lacking democratic legitimacy,¹² our focus is more urgent: the simple but vital principle that law must be free. We show how, following the *Malamud* decision, the EU already has the legal tools to unlock access—and that doing so is possible and necessary. Finally, we also point out certain open questions regarding access to other legally significant instruments that remain despite the *Malamud* case, i.e. whether related documents such as technical reports—essential for interpreting harmonised standards—must also be made freely available, and whether limiting access to read-only versions truly meets the requirement of full legal accessibility.

2. The Case that opened the Code: Malamud and the fight for free Standards

In 2024, the *Public.Resource.Org Inc. v European Commission* case—now known simply as the *Malamud* case—was brought by non-profit organizations demanding one simple thing: that the public should be able to read the rules that govern them. They sought free access to four harmonized standards—three were referenced in the Toy Safety Directive, and one was used to verify compliance with the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation, and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH) Regulation. Though functionally essential for legal compliance, these documents were only available behind

¹² Rossana Ducato, ‘Why Harmonised Standards Should Be Open’ (2023) 54 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 1173.

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paywalls. When the applicants invoked their rights of access to EU documents,¹³ the Commission refused, arguing that releasing the standards would violate commercial interests and intellectual property rights of private standardization bodies. The General Court accepted this argument.

On appeal, however, the European Court of Justice (ECJ) overturned that decision—marking a turning point in EU legal doctrine on accessibility and standardization. The ECJ relied on legal groundwork laid in earlier rulings. In *Fra.bo SpA v Deutsche Vereinigung des Gas- und Wasserfaches eV*,¹⁴ the Court held that private technical standards could fall within the scope of EU law if they influenced market access. In *James Elliot Construction Limited v Irish Asphalt Limited*,¹⁵ it ruled that harmonized standards referenced in EU legislation could be treated as part of that law. Building on these precedents, the ECJ in *Malamud* took the next logical step: if harmonised standards form part of EU law, the public must have a right to access them.

This was far from a symbolic gesture. The Court anchored its reasoning in the rule of law and the need for practical—not merely theoretical—access to legal norms. It stated plainly that legal obligations must be known to all, without cost, and decisively

¹³ Regulation (EC) No 1049/2001 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2001 regarding public access to European Parliament, Council and Commission documents 2001 (OJ L 145) 43, art 2.

¹⁴ *Fra.bo SpA v Deutsche Vereinigung des Gas- und Wasserfaches eV* [2012] European Court of Justice Case C-171/11, ECLI:EU:C:2012:453.

¹⁵ *James Elliot Construction Limited v Irish Asphalt Limited* [2016] European Court of Justice Case C-613/14, ECLI:EU:C:2016:821.

rejected the Commission’s view that copyright protections or commercial interests could justify keeping binding standards behind paywalls.

The Court essentially ruled that there is an overriding public interest in providing access to the documents requested. This principle matters because EU legal systems upholds *ignorantia juris non excusat*—ignorance of the law is no excuse. Yet, when essential legal instruments are hidden behind a checkout screen, how can the public realistically comply? Denying access to the law fundamentally contradicts this foundational principle.

Critics have expressed concern about the judgment’s implications for intellectual property regimes and the financing of standardization bodies.¹⁶ However, as others have rightly pointed out, these concerns cannot outweigh the principles of legal certainty and democratic legitimacy.¹⁷ The *Malamud* decision is, in our view, a necessary course correction: when harmonized standards are gatekeepers to legal compliance, they must be free.

3. Putting the Malamud Case to the test: Can robot standards be made free?

The *Malamud* ruling affirmed the right to access harmonised standards. However, what happens when that right is tested in practice—particularly in the highly technical field of robotics? Assessing the legal compliance of personal care robots, for instance,

¹⁶ Eleni Tzouliia, ‘Harmonized Standards in the Public Domain? Better Not ...’ (2025) 56 IIC - International Review of Intellectual Property and Competition Law 692.

¹⁷ Olya Kanevskaia, ‘Is It Really All about the Money? The Future of European Standardization after PublicResourceOrg’ (2025) 16 European Journal of Risk Regulation 344.

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involves navigating a complex web of interdependent standards. At the core lies ISO 13482:2014—the only harmonized standard in the EU specifically addressing non-industrial, non-medical service robots.¹⁸ However, legal conformity is not determined by this standard alone. Related harmonized standards, such as ISO 13849-1:2015 (concerning the safety of machinery control systems) and IEC 62061:2021 (on the functional safety of electrical systems), are also relevant. In addition, two technical reports—ISO/TR 23482-1:2020 and ISO/TR 23482-2:2019—are essential for understanding and applying ISO 13482:2014 in practice. Although these reports are not themselves harmonized standards, they provide the necessary interpretive guidance to assess legal compliance.

Together, these documents form the core regulatory framework for ensuring the safety and legal conformity of personal care robots. Manufacturers, market surveillance authorities, legal experts, and researchers, they all depend on them. Yet, despite their critical role in shaping access to the European market and upholding public safety, these standards remain commercially restricted. Moreover, because they are periodically revised, ensuring continued access may require repeated payments over time, creating both legal and financial barriers to compliance.

To assess whether the *Malamud* ruling has practical force, we submitted a request for access through the Commission’s website¹⁹ for three key documents: ISO 13482:2014, ISO/TR 23482-1:2020, and ISO/TR 23482-2:2019. Our request explained

¹⁸ Soon to be replaced by ISO 13482:2025 Robotics — Safety requirements for service robots.

¹⁹ ‘Electronic Access to Commission Documents (EASE)’ <<https://ec.europa.eu/transparency/documents-request/home>> accessed 4 March 2025.

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how each document directly relates to EU law and the principles established in the *Malamud* judgment. In response, the Commission granted access only to ISO 13482:2014, now available through the eNorm portal²⁰—but solely as a read-only version that cannot be downloaded or shared. The eNorm platform provides read-only access to harmonised standards and the users are to use their EU login (user authentication by the Commission) to view the standards on the platform. However, the Commission denied access to the two technical reports on the grounds that they are not harmonized standards and are, therefore, not held by the Commission.

We filed an appeal, arguing that these technical reports are essential for interpreting and implementing the harmonized standard ISO 13482:2014 and should, therefore, fall under the *Malamud* precedent. The appeal was dismissed. The Commission maintained that it has no obligation to release non-harmonized documents, even if they are functionally indispensable—on the basis that such documents are not in its possession.

Figure 1 summarises the practical steps involved in requesting access to harmonised standards and the potential outcomes at each stage (including with respect to the appeal process). We provide this as a broad guide for others seeking to obtain harmonised standards under the *Malamud* ruling, since the process may not always be obvious or straightforward.

²⁰ ‘eNorm Platform’ <https://ec.europa.eu/growth/tools-databases/enorm/access_to_harmonised_standards> accessed 21 July 2025.

Figure 1. Pathway for free access to Harmonised Standards

This case study highlights the limitations of the *Malamud* ruling when applied in complex regulatory ecosystems. Although the decision opens access to harmonised standards, the interpretive documents that give those standards practical meaning remain locked behind paywalls. It is our understanding, however, that when legal compliance depends on an interlocking set of documents, withholding any of that system undermines the intent of the Court’s decision and intent, and erodes meaningful public access to the law.

4. Access denied? What the *Malamud* Case means for robotics regulation

The ECJ's ruling in the *Malamud* case marked a turning point for legal access in the EU. By affirming that harmonized standards referenced in legislation must be freely available, the Court set a precedent with profound implications for technology governance. This is especially significant in fast-evolving sectors such as robotics (and potentially AI), where regulation often relies not on laws alone but on technical standards that fill legislative gaps. From personal care robots to AI-enabled machinery, these standards shape how safety, accountability, and compliance are defined across the EU. When such standards carry legal weight, access to them is not a matter of convenience—it is a matter of rights.

The *Malamud* ruling provides a strong legal basis for opening harmonised standards to public access. Yet, key issues remain unresolved. One unresolved issue is whether limiting access to 'read-only' versions—without the ability to download or share—meets the threshold of full legal accessibility.²¹ More critically, the Court did not clarify whether related documents such as technical reports—essential for interpreting harmonized standards—must also be made freely available. As our own efforts show, the Commission maintains that it cannot release non-harmonized texts that are not in its possession, even if they are essential to understanding the applicable law.

This creates a troubling contradiction: the law demands that no one can plead ignorance, yet it fails to ensure that the law is entirely knowable. The principle of *ignorantia juris non excusat* presumes that legal norms are accessible, transparent, and stable. This gap is especially serious because compliance for many products, including

²¹ Kanevskaia (n 17).

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robots and AI systems, is demonstrated through CE marking and conformity assessment procedures that rely directly on these standards. Without access to all the instruments necessary for compliance, especially in highly technical fields like robotics and AI, the foundational principle of legal certainty is undermined. Citizens and companies alike are expected to obey rules they may neither read nor understand—exposing a stark gap between legal theory and regulatory practice.

In a regulatory landscape already marked by overlapping and evolving rules—and what scholars have called “competing legal futures” for AI and digital innovation²²—keeping essential standards behind paywalls adds an unnecessary barrier. This undermines the very goals of the New Legislative Framework, which seeks to simplify the rules for placing a wide range of products on the EU market.

We, therefore, conclude with a clear imperative: all harmonized standards and their interpretive instruments—especially those underpinning AI, robotics, and machine regulation—must be freely and fully accessible, because legal obligations should never depend on one’s ability to pay, nor should the law to remain behind a paywall.

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²² Marco Giraudo, Eduard Fosch-Villaronga and Gianclaudio Malgieri, ‘Competing legal futures –

“commodification bets” all the way from personal data to AI’ (2024) 25 *German Law Journal* 1095.